

**JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTGA OID MASALALARNI HAL QILISHDA
ELEKTRON JADVALNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI VA IMKONIYATLARIDAN
FOYDALANISH.**

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Annotasiya. Jismoniy tarbiya va sportdan olingan ko'rsatkichlarni microsoft excel dasturi yordamida tahlil qilish usularini o'rganish.

Kalit so'zlar: Brave-Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti, Spirmenning rangga oid korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti, funktsiyalar ustasi.

**USING THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS AND POSSIBILITIES OF THE
ELECTRONIC SCHEDULE IN SOLVING ISSUES RELATED TO PHYSICAL
EDUCATION AND SPORTS.**

Abstract. To study the methods of analysis of indicators obtained from physical education and sports using Microsoft Excel.

Keywords: Brave-Pearson's correlation coefficient, Spearman's color correlation coefficient, function master.

**ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК И ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ
ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО РАСПИСАНИЯ ПРИ РЕШЕНИИ ВОПРОСОВ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С
ФИЗИЧЕСКИМ ВОСПИТАНИЕМ И СПОРТОМ.**

Аннотация. Изучить методы анализа показателей, полученных по физическому воспитанию и спорту, с использованием Microsoft Excel.

Ключевые слова: коэффициент корреляции Брейва-Пирсона, коэффициент цветовой корреляции Спирмена, функция хозяина.

MS Excel dasturida kiritilgan ma'lumotlarni Funktsiya masteri yordamida tahlil qilish. Brave-Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti va Spirmenning rangga oid korrelyatsiya koeffitsientini qo'llashga oid misollar echish.

Bir guruh suzuvchilarning tanasi absolyut yuzalarining son qiymati X (m^2) va og'irliklari Y (kg) o'lchanganda quyidagi natijalar olindi.

X : 1,86; 1,76; 1,74; 1,80; 1,68; 1,81; 1,71; 1,80;

Y : 69, 64, 63, 67, 60, 66, 63, 58.

Tana og'irligi bilan uning absolyut yuzalari orasidagi korrelyatsiya koeffitsienti sportchilar guruhi uchun keltirilgan natijalarga asosan aniqlansin. Bu misolda o'lchash natijalarining soni, ya'ni tanlanma hajmi $n = 8$.

Buning uchun Brave-Pirsonning korrelyatsiya koeffitsientini hisoblash zarur.

Hisoblash jarayonini MS Excel dasturi yordamida bosqichma-bosqich bayon etamiz.

Ishning bajarilish tartibi.

1. MS Excel dasturini ishga tushiring.

2. Natijalarni tahlil qilish uchun ko'rsatgan natijalarini MS Excel dasturining ishchi maydoniga kiriting.

	A	B	C
1	№	X	Y
2	1	1,86	69
3	2	1,76	64
4	3	1,74	63
5	4	1,8	67
6	5	1,68	60
7	6	1,81	66
8	7	1,71	63
9	8	1,8	68

X va Y ustunlar bo'yicha Summani Σ va O'rtacha qiymatlarni CP3HA4 funksiyalari yordamida aniqlang.

Buning uchun X ustunini belgilab olib, Стандартная asboblar panelidagi Σ belgisi yordamida ustundagi sonlar yig'indisi aniqlanadi.

X va Y ustunlar bo'yicha natijalarning o'rtacha qiymatlarini Функция masteri yordamida aniqlanadi. Buning uchun, Функция ustasi maydonga chaqiriladi CP3HA4 funksiyasi tanlanib, OK tugmasi bosiladi. «Аргумент функции» muloqot oynasiga sonlar diapazoni ko'rsatiladi, ya'ni, X ustunidagi sonlarni belgilab OK tugmasi bosiladi. Natijani dastur belgilangan katakchga joylashtiradi.

	A	B	C
1	№	X	Y
2	1	1,86	69
3	2	1,76	64
4	3	1,74	63
5	4	1,8	67
6	5	1,68	60
7	6	1,81	66
8	7	1,71	63
9	8	1,8	68
10	$\Sigma =$	14,16	520
11	Срзнач	1,77	65

3. Keyingi ustunni to'ldirish uchun $(X-X_0)$ funktsiyaning qiymatini aniqlaymiz. Har bir X ning qiymatidan X ning o'rtacha qiymatni ayiramiz. Agar formulani kiritib aftoto'ldirish markeri bilan to'dirsak, noto'g'ri natija beradi. Bu erda yuqorida aytib o'tilgan absolyut katakchani ishlatish o'rni keldi. Buning uchun, formula kiritilib, katakchamizni mutloq qilish uchun F4 tugmachamizni bosamiz, natijada quyidagi manzara hosil bo'ladi.

4. Mana endi to'ldirish markerini ishlatsak ham bo'ladi. $(Y-Y_0)$ funktsiyaning qiymatini aniqlashda ham huddi shu punktlarni amalga oshiramiz.

5. $(X-X_0)$ va $(Y-Y_0)$ funktsiya qiymatlar yig'indisi nolga teng bo'lganligi sababli, keyingi ustunda ularni ko'paytiramiz.

	A	B	C	D	E
1	№	X	Y	$(X-\bar{X})$	$(Y-\bar{Y})$
2	1	1,86	69	0,09	4
3	2	1,76	64	-0,01	-1
4	3	1,74	63	-0,03	-2
5	4	1,8	67	0,03	2
6	5	1,68	60	-0,09	-5
7	6	1,81	66	0,04	1
8	7	1,71	63	-0,06	-2
9	8	1,8	68	0,03	3
10	$\Sigma =$	14,16	520		
11	Срзнач	1,77	65		

6. formuladan foydalanib X ko'rsatkich uchun ayirmaning kvadratlar yig'indisini aniqlaymiz. Buning uchun, $(X-X_0)$ qiymatlarini kvadratga olamiz. Funktsiyalar ustasidan foydalangan holda Степень darajaga olinishni murojaat qilamiz. «Аргумент функции» muloqot oynasida son turgan katakchamizga murojaat qilamiz va pastdagi darchaga 2 sonini kiritamiz.

7. (Y-Yo'p) qiymatlarini kvadratga olishda ham shu punktlar amalga oshiriladi. Yig'indi hisoblanadi.

8. Ishni bajarganingizdan keyin quyidagi jadval hosil bo'ladi.

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